

Species 1: *H. hecalesia*

NOT test

Species 2: *H. clysonimus*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D = 0.246

Background 2->1

Background 1->2

Species 1: *H. hecalesia*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.45; high PNT

NDT test

Species 2: *H. clysonimus*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.61; high PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1

Red=S1>S2, Blue=S1<S2, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.179

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.236

Background 2->1

D
p.value = 0.00325

Background 1->2

D
p.value = 0.01316